

Curriculum Management for the Society's Development in Mozambique

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Abstract:- The study of Buleque (2020) indicated that curriculum management brings in different academic results between pupils of private and government schools Mozambique, this motivated this study entitled “Curriculum management for the society’s development in Mozambique”, to be carried out. This aims to explain how school curriculum can be managed for the development of society. Therefore, documental and bibliographic data were collected and analyzed in order to carry out the present study. The results indicated that curriculum management has to be within content and it requires the focus on its origin so that can produce results that can enable the development of the society.

Keywords:- society, curriculum, development, management.

I. INTRODUCTION

School curriculum is considered as the heart of any learning institution which means that schools or universities cannot exist without a curriculum. This means that, with its importance in formal education, the curriculum has become a dynamic process due to the changes that occur in our society. Therefore, in its broadest sense, curriculum refers to the complete learning experiences of individuals not only in school, but in society as well, (Bilbao et al. 2008).

According to Alvior (2014), curriculum management for the society’s development in the ancient times; is about when parents taught their children knowledge and skills to survive by catching fish or hunting animals for food. They had no formal education during that time, but their children learned and acquired the knowledge and skills for survival. In Mozambique, there are a lot of natural resources, gas and different type minerals but yet people are very. Therefore, this study seeks to understand the how can school curriculum be managed for development of the society.

II. PROBLEMATIZATION

The study carried out in 2020, indicated that there is difference academic performance between grade pupils from private and government primary schools as the results of curriculum management styles (Buleque, 2020). This means that, poverty in Mozambique can be the results of curriculum management failure. Therefore, this study seeks to answer the following question: How can school curriculum can be managed for the development of society?

III. CURRICULUM MANAGEMENT IN ANCIENT TIMES

It is believed that primitive men had procedures of teaching their children so that can be able to learn to something for their survival. During that time, they already had a curriculum that other educators call the *saber-tooth* curriculum (Peddiwell, 2004). This type of curriculum management refers to a kind of curriculum that existed during the ancient times in which the purpose of teaching was for survival. However, when the effects of discoveries and inventions became inevitable, ancient people’s way of life had changed for the better. As a result, education became formal, and curriculum development evolved as systematic, planned, purposeful and progressive, even today (Tanner & Tanner, 2007). Therefore, there must be a chain of developmental process to develop a society. This process begins with the school curriculum management able to equip children with required abilities and knowledge, particularly in primary school, and this must be developed to preserve the country’s national identity and to ensure its economy’s growth and stability (Kim, 2004).

The Bible in the book of Proverbs (22:6) explains the importance of teaching young people by saying that “train up a child in the way he should go, when he is old he will not depart from it”. Based on this argument, we can understand that as a nation the leader of a country must have a clear vision for his people and the country as well by making sure that children are learning what is necessary and important. In so doing, the country’s economy and the people’s way of life can improve through curriculum management.

Farrant (2004) argues that the curriculum should be dynamic and impress on the philosophy and educational purposes of the school and the nation. Impressing on the philosophy, in this study, refers to the impartiality of the rules that regulate the philosophy of education that must be applied to both government and private schools. This can be possible if the school leadership know better what and how to teach the children and manage the curriculum. The next section presents the theoretical framework borrowed in order to build this research.

IV. CURRICULUM MANAGEMENT AS PRODUCTION FUNCTIONS

This section views curriculum management in standard theories of economics, where production functions are defined as the maximum output that can be obtained by using a combination of inputs. These have been applied to many industries. Researchers also applied this approach to education and production functions which are an important tool for analysing the efficiency of the education process. Curriculum management, as production functions, can be understood as the relationship between quantity and quality

of inputs used in the process of curriculum implementation and the output of the process (Hanushek, 1995). However, the production function of education has some particular characteristics, such as: class size, teacher experience, and teacher education – bear little systematic relationship to student outcomes, implying that conventional input policies are unlikely to improve achievement.

V. EFFECTIVENESS BARRIER OF CURRICULUM MANAGEMENT AS PRODUCTION FUNCTIONS

Firstly, the production function is not widely known to policymakers. Secondly, it is difficult to measure outcomes in education. Education outputs are both quantitative and qualitative. On the same note, the quantitative part of education is related to output in terms of number of learners who finish a given level of education. On the other note, the qualitative part is connected to the provision of academic performance results such as writing, reading and counting as well examination results, (Hanushek, 2008). The researcher visualises the combination of these facts of the complexity of the educational production process as illustrated in the Figure 1 .

Fig. 1: Process of curriculum management

Figure 1 demonstrates the curriculum management process that (a) represents the society, which means that the curriculum is planned, and designed to satisfy the needs of the society. It is also the responsibility of the society to provide the inputs for the curriculum management and implementation. (b) are the inputs, that include the infrastructure, learning and teaching materials, time spent by teachers and other staff and also the time spent by the pupil. Cohn and Geske (1990) divide inputs into two categories: school inputs and non-school inputs. School inputs include human and physical resources. The physical inputs are constituted by equipment and materials to support the learning process; human resources are constituted by quantity and quality of the teachers, managers and administrative

personnel. Cohn and Geske (1990) posit that policymakers should support teachers more due to the fact that a great part of the budget is spent on this human input. It is important to mention that aspects like qualification and teaching vocation should be considered as inputs to the process. (c) indicates that pupils or students are the raw materials provided from the society to the school for transformation into products ready to be used in the society. Furthermore, (d) is the centre or the school where the production functions take place and (e) is production functions' results and pupils' academic performance results.

VI. SCHOOL AS THE CENTRE OF PRODUCTION FUNCTIONS

The process of production function in education takes place in schools. Better allocation of resources does not necessarily imply better pupil performance. It is necessary also that the production process, which takes place in school, should be efficient. Improvement in efficiency can be interpreted as increasing outputs without additional resources (Hanushek, 2008). Mazula (2016) explains that the school cannot become the centre of productions function without better curriculum management, and he also explains that Mozambique is the country with full of natural and mineral resources but the it is funny to see schools without desks.

Cohn and Geske (1990) say that the production process is influenced by the incentives, management and organisation, and the learning process. Therefore, the improvements in curriculum management should take into consideration factors like planning, organising, motivating people, and control of the production process. Attention to the process of production ensures better pupils' academic performance. Hanushek and Luque (2002, p. 20-21) studied the efficiency and equity in a sample schools of the world. They found that school performance is related to efficient use of resources. Policies such as teacher training and reducing pupil-teacher ratios are not always effective means to improve performance. It is necessary to improve organisational aspects of the schools and also avail incentives to the participants of the process. This study sought to examine how curriculum management styles applied in the public and private primary schools of Quelimane city, Zambezi Province in Mozambique influenced availability of resources and brought about the difference in academic performance of the children in reading, writing, counting and Grade Seven results. The next section discusses the concept of pupils as outputs in the production process.

VII. PUPILS AS THE OUTPUTS

The curriculum management brings out outputs to the society; these outputs are the pupils' academic achievement. Vaizey (1971) posits that the outputs can be measured in followings ways:

- The number of pupils that finished school;
- What every pupil learned in that period;
- Pupils who pass their examinations in the year;
- Improvements in social aspects of the pupils (the last is difficult to measure).

Output in curriculum management is a result of the inputs allocated to the production process and the way that these inputs are transformed into outcomes or outputs (Vaizey,1971). It is important to measure pupils' academic performance based on the number of pupils that completed the school level, as well as the improvements in social aspects of the pupils in order to understand the effects of curriculum management. However, in this study, the researchers concentrated on Grade 7 pupils' examination performance based on the previous different examination results between government and private primary schools. It was noted that private primary pupils present necessary basic skills, whereby

government primary school pupils do not have basic skills acquired from schools.

Cohn and Geske (1990) divide outputs of schools into five categories: 1) Basic skills; (2) Vocational skills; 3) Creativity; 4) Attitudes; and 5) Other outputs. A pupil obtains basic skills when he or she knows the essentials of mathematics and language. Vocational skills are job-oriented. The capacity to use education to individual and social benefit is known as creativity. The influence that school has on pupils, in terms of behaviour in society, is known as 'attitudes'. Finally, among other outputs are that some schools work as welfare stations, providing aid to poor people or child care facilities to working parents. Therefore, this study examined academic performance in terms of the pupils being able to acquire basic skills such as writing, reading and mathematics calculations.

VIII. CONCLUSION

In this study the researchers concluded that in the curriculum management process, the inputs of the education process are constituted by school inputs; these inputs have an important influence on the success of the curriculum management as education production process. In this sense, the curriculum management and implementation is the production process within schools and is an important factor in improving the society's development.

There is optimism that related literature has covered strides in establishing what various researchers regard as the role of curriculum management in academic performance of pupils in the primary school. The review of related literature has also highlighted the researchers was confident that the study would contribute towards filling this gap. Therefore, it was noted that the viability of curriculum management, as a major factor that influence academic performance of pupils, is still a subject for debate in academic and professional circles that can brings the society's development in Mozambique.

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